

Variation in salt tolerance of rice plants regenerated from salt-selected calli of a susceptible variety

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The variety Mot Bui is popular in deep-water areas of the Cuu Long Delta of Vietnam. It is, however, salt-susceptible. We attempted to induce somaclonal variation for salt tolerance from this variety. The mature seeds were cultured on MS medium (supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹, 30 g sucrose L⁻¹ and 8 g agar L⁻¹) for callus induction.

After three subcultures, the embryo-derived calli were transferred to the same medium containing 1.5% NaCl. After 1 mo, the calli that survived and grew normally under salt stress were transferred

Efficiency in selection of salt-tolerant calli and its effect on plant regeneration.

Description	Number or Percentage
Calli cultured in salt medium (no.)	4050
Salt-tolerant calli selected (no.)	214 (5.3%)
Salt-tolerant calli transferred to regeneration medium (no.)	214
Calli producing green shoots (no.)	48 (22.4%)
Calli producing green shoots out of total calli cultured in salt medium (%)	1.2
Total R ₀ , regenerated plants	120

to the regeneration medium (MS medium supplemented with 2 mg kinetin L⁻¹, 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹, 30 g sucrose L⁻¹, and 8 g agar L⁻¹). Once rooted, the regenerated plants (R₀ generation) were grown in a nutrient solution; upon reaching 15 cm, they were transferred to the nutrient solution supplemented with NaCl to get a salt level expressed by EC of 12 dS m⁻¹. The survival rate of the regenerated plants was recorded after 2 wk. The check varieties included Pokkali (tolerant), IR28 (susceptible), and the

parent variety Mot Bui. Another set of the regenerated plants was grown under normal conditions to obtain R₁ somaclones, and their tolerance for salt was evaluated following the procedures described above.

Out of 4,050 calli subjected to in vitro salt selection, most turned brown and died, but 214 showed normal growth. Of these calli, 48 produced green shoots when cultured on the regeneration medium (see table). The percentage of calli producing shoots to total number of calli cultured on the salt medium was 1.2. We screened regenerated plants (R₀ generation) and found that 35% of them survived after 2 wk under salt stress, while all of the plants of Mot Bui and IR28 died. In the next generation, 34 R₁ somaclones were evaluated for salt tolerance at the seedling stage (9 d old). Twenty-eight somaclones (23.5%) were salt-tolerant. This study suggests that variation for salt tolerance exists among lines derived from salt-tolerant calli of a salt-susceptible rice variety. ■

Genetics of salinity tolerance and ionic uptake in rice

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Increasing salinity of soil and water is a serious threat to agriculture. Breeding for salt tolerance offers a more promising, energy-efficient, economical, and socially acceptable approach to solving these problems than do major engineering processes and soil amelioration.

Salt-tolerant rice as a biological amendment for managing salt-affected soils has been demonstrated (Mishra 1994). Improving salt tolerance requires systematic genetic studies. Reliability of reproductive phase salinity tolerance score with grain yield was strongly correlated under both

controlled and field conditions (Mishra 1994). Grain yield was also strongly correlated with K⁺ uptake and Na-K ratio in the shoot. Based on these relationships, we investigated the genetics of salinity tolerance at the reproductive stage and K⁺ and Na-K ratio in the shoot in a 6 × 6 half-diallel cross involving tolerant (CSR10, CSRI, and Nona Bokra) and susceptible (IR28, M1-48, and Basmati 370) parents in an artificially created saline soil environment (ECe = 10-14 dS m⁻¹) at IRR. Salinity stress was developed with NaCl + CaCl₂ in a 1:1 ratio by weight and maintained by continuous recycling. Na and K concentrations in the shoot were analyzed on an oven dry weight basis. Data were analyzed by both the Hayman (1954) and Griffing (1956) methods.

Analysis of variance showed highly significant genetic variations among the parents and F₁s for salinity tolerance score at the reproductive phase, K concentration, and Na-K ratio. The reduction in grain yield was 28.9% in tolerant variety CSR10

while susceptible variety IR28 showed 98.2% yield reduction. K⁺ absorption was maximum in CSR1 (2.31%) followed by CSR10 (2.27%); it was least in IR28 (2.06%). Low Na-K ratio resulted in better salinity tolerance. The lowest Na-K ratio was in CSR10 (tolerant) and highest in M1-48 (susceptible), thus revealing the significance of K⁺ uptake in salt tolerance.

Estimates of genetic parameters following Hayman's method showed significant additive and nonadditive gene action for salinity tolerance score, K⁺ and Na-K ratio (Table 1). Narrow-sense heritability estimates were 0.65 for salinity tolerance score, 0.55 for K⁺ absorption, and 0.41 for Na-K ratio. The presence of gene asymmetry for salinity tolerance score and Na-K ratio and gene symmetry for K⁺ was detected. Average dominance was within the range of incomplete dominance. This suggested that one group of genes is involved in salinity tolerance score and Na-K ratio and two groups in K⁺ uptake. Recessive alleles were more concentrated

Table 1. Estimates of genetic parameters for reproductive stage salinity tolerance score and K concentration and Na-K ratio in shoots of 6 × 6 diallel.

Genetic parameter	Estimate ± SE					
	Salinity tolerance score		K		Na-K	
D	10.760* ^a	± 1.080	0.056*	± 0.009	0.099*	± 0.017
H ₁	7.532*	± 2.916	0.067*	± 0.024	0.129*	± 0.044
H ₂	5.536*	± 2.645	0.056*	± 0.022	0.092*	± 0.039
h ²	3.299	± 1.786	0.075*	± 0.015	0.030	± 0.027
F	6.663*	± 2.698	0.004	± 0.023	0.096*	± 0.043
E	0.290	± 0.441	0.012*	± 0.004	0.006	± 0.007
Proportional values						
(H ₁ /D) ^{1/2}	0.837		1.091		1.139	
H ₂ /4H ₁	0.184		0.210		0.178	
[(4DH ₁) ^{1/2} + F]/ [(4DH ₁) ^{1/2} - F]	2.175		1.062		2.484	
r (Wr + Vr)/Yr	0.96		0.60		0.971	
h ₂ /H ₂	0.596		1.326		0.324	
h ² (narrow sense)	0.65		0.55		0.410	

^a * = significant at the 5% level.

than dominant genes in the tolerant varieties CSR10 and CSRI for salinity tolerance score at the reproductive phase and K⁺ uptake while dominant alleles were more concentrated than recessive in Nona Bokra, CSR10, and CSRI in that order. Wr-Vr graphic analysis suggested the involvement of both major and minor genes for all the traits investigated.

Combining ability analysis by Griffing's method confirmed the significance of both additive and nonadditive effects, with additive effects showing greater importance in the inheritance of the traits (Table 2). The

varieties CSR10 and CSRI were good general combiners for all three traits examined and could be useful in rice breeding programs aiming to improve salt tolerance. High heterotic effects found in some crosses suggest the potential of hybrid rice for salt-affected soils. CSR10 is now being used as a donor in an India-IRRI collaborative project on salinity tolerance and also as a low-cost biological amendment for managing salt-affected soils in India.

Table 2. Combining ability analysis for salinity tolerance score at reproductive stage and K concentration and Na-K ratio in shoots of 6 × 6 diallel.

Source	df	Mean square		
		Salinity tolerance score at reproductive stage	K	Na-K ratio
gca	5	15.36** ^a	0.238**	0.100**
sca	15	3.71**	0.065**	0.033**
Error	40	0.22	0.012	0.006
gca/sca		4.14	3.66	3.03

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

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Stress tolerance

Epigenetic control of tolerance for transient low light stress in rice

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Rice has smaller photosynthetic capacity and less accumulation of assimilates—resulting in a low yield—under low light stress than does rice grown under adequate solar radiation. For example, rice yield during the wet season is 65.2% of that

during the dry season (Murty and Sahu, 1987), and rice that receives half of the full sunshine has 57% less yield than rice receiving full sunshine (Murty 1992). Tolerance for low light stress is genetically controlled, but until recently little has been known about the genes involved. To explore whether cytoplasmic genes are involved in controlling this physiological character, we used several sets of reciprocal cross combinations in which double parents show typical tolerance for or sensitivity to transient low light stress.

Detached flag leaves at the heading stage were inserted into tap water and equilibrated under near saturated light intensity (500 μE m²s⁻¹). For a different set of leaves, light intensity was rapidly decreased to 110 μE m²s⁻¹ and leaves were

incubated for 1 min under low irradiation. At the same time, net photosynthesis rates (Pn, μmol CO₂ m²s⁻¹) in two light environments (expressed as Pn 500 and Pn 110) were determined with a LI-6200 photosynthesis system. To indicate the degree of Pn decrease immediately after irradiation, we used (Pn 500-Pn 110)/Pn 500. The threshold was determined to be half of the decrease of Pn(max) at 110 μE m²s⁻¹. The leaves were tolerant when their Pn changes were below the threshold or sensitive when Pn changes were over the threshold under transient light stress. Data in the table were averages of 3-6 repetitions.

Eight sets of combination among the 11 parents (see table) were classified into three kinds according to the degree of Pn reduction of the parents: 1) both parents have a